

Spectral studies and lattice parameters of nickel(II) and palladium(II) complexes with 5-nitrosalicyldoxime

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5-Nitrosalicyldoxime has been synthesized by reacting 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde with hydroxylamine hydrochloride. This oxime is used to synthesised nickel(II) and palladium(II) complexes having 1 : 2 metal-ligand stoichiometry. The XRD data are used to index the compound for monoclinic system with space group $P2_1m$.

Literature reports the structural aspects and reactivity of transition metal oxime complexes¹. However, the elucidation of structure in terms of lattice parameters using X-ray powder diffractogram data is a shortcoming in this field. It is therefore worthwhile investigating the crystallographic nature of nickel(II) and palladium(II) complexes derived from 5-nitrosalicyldoxime.

Results and Discussion

Both the crystalline complexes $Ni(C_7H_5N_2O_4)_2$ (green) and $Pd(C_7H_5N_2O_4)_2$ (yellow) are sparingly soluble in common organic solvents, but soluble in DMSO and nitrobenzene. The neutral nature of the complexes is indicated by low values of their molar conductivity (10.4×10^{-3} to 10.8×10^{-3} S) in DMSO². The elemental analyses data reveal 1 : 2 M : L stoichiometry for both the complexes. Both the compounds are diamagnetic in nature³. Agarwal and Agarwal⁴ reported diamagnetic Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes of phenylazo-bis-benzaldoxime. The square-planar geometry of the Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes is evident from their diamagnetic nature⁵.

The electronic absorption spectra of the Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes appear similar, showing bands around 27000 cm^{-1} assigned to metal-to-ligand charge transfer⁶. The spectra of the diamagnetic Ni^{II} complex exhibited bands at 11494, 16120 and 24390 cm^{-1} , assigned to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g}$ (ν_1), $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$ (ν_2) and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1E_{1g}$ (ν_3) transitions in square-planar Ni^{II} environment⁶. The spectra of the diamagnetic Pd^{II} complex exhibited weak bands at 11494 and 21739 cm^{-1} , and a strong band at 25000 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to $d-d$ transitions².

The IR spectra of 5-nitrosalicyldoxime showed bands at 3350 (OH) and at 1620 cm^{-1} (C=N). The Ni^{II} and Pd^{II}

complexes showed bands at 3100 and 3250 cm^{-1} , respectively, assigned to ν_{O-H} stretching vibrations⁷, which indicates that out of the phenolic and oximic hydroxyl groups, only one is involved in coordination with the metal ion. The oximic hydroxyl group is not deprotonated due to its higher pK_a value. Similarly, the $\nu_{C=N}$ vibrations in the Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes were observed at 1600 and 1590 cm^{-1} , respectively. The shift in the position of $\nu_{C=N}$ stretching vibrations by 20–30 cm^{-1} indicates the involvement of oximic nitrogen in coordination with the metal ion⁸. The involvement of oximic nitrogen and phenolic oxygen in coordination with the metal ion is further established on the basis of the appearance of new bands at 620–630 (M–N) and 420–475 cm^{-1} (M–O)⁹. The tentative structure assigned on the basis of spectral characterization is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1

The X-ray diffractograms of the Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes indicate high crystallinity of these complexes. The major reflexes were measured and the corresponding d -values were obtained. An independent indexing for each of these reflexes was carried out by least-square method. The Miller indices (hkl) were calculated and refined using Back-Cal program by computational method. The lattice parameter obtained for the Ni^{II} complex are $a = 14.7652 \pm 0.0372$, $b = 10.1076 \pm 0.0373$, $c = 38.6594 \pm 0.1099$ Å and $\beta = 23^\circ 23'$ and those of the Pd^{II} complex are $a = 14.6501 \pm 0.0469$, $b = 10.2746 \pm 0.0378$, $c = 38.5777 \pm 0.1682$ Å and $\beta = 23^\circ 32'$. The cell volume obtained for the Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes

are 2275.7640 and 2298.7770 Å³, respectively. The Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes can be successfully indexed to monoclinic system with formula factor ($Z = 4$). The correctness of the above values were confirmed by matching the observed density ($D_{\text{obs}} = 1.32$ for the Ni^{II} complex and $D_{\text{obs}} = 1.42$ g cm⁻³ for the Pd^{II} complex) with the calculated values ($D_{\text{cal}} = 1.23$ for Ni^{II} complex and 1.35 g cm⁻³ for Pd^{II} complex) from the X-ray diffractograms. The hkl values for each reflexes were examined closely to assign space group $P_{2/m}$ to both these complexes using literature data¹⁰. The assignment of space group further confirms definite crystal system with authenticity. However, the X-ray diffraction studies and space group is unable to indicate the formation of multinuclear metal complexes.

It may be concluded that the Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes possess square-planar structure with phenolic oxygen and oxyimine nitrogen as coordinating groups. The compounds crystallize in a monoclinic system with space group $P_{2/m}$ with $Z = 4$.

Experimental

All the chemicals and solvents used were of synthesis grade. The ligand 5-nitrosalicylaldoxime was obtained from oximation of 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde¹¹. The methanolic solution of the recrystallized oxime (1%, w/v) was mixed with the metal solution (1 mg cm⁻³). The pH of the reaction mixture was adjusted to 7 in case of Ni^{II} and 3 in case of Pd^{II} complex. The resulting solid complexes were washed with hot aqueous methanol, dried and crystallized from methanol (yield ≈65%). The compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

The magnetic moment was determined by Gouy's method. Electronic and diffused reflectance spectra (BaSO₄) were measured on a Shimadzu UV-VIS-2100 spectrophotometer and IR spectra on a Shimadzu FTIR-4200 spectrophotometer. Molar conductivity in DMSO was measured on a Toshniwal CL01.10A conductivity meter. The X-ray diffractograms were recorded on a Shimadzu 6000 instrument using CuK_α radiations (CuK_α = 1.5418 Å) and scanned in the range, $2\theta = 5-60^\circ$.

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